

An Academic AI Search Engine Checklist— April 2025 (version)

When choosing an academic AI search engine, consider criteria including:

1. Your research needs & functionality and capabilities of the tools
2. Data privacy and security
3. Considerations related to intellectual property
4. Ethical considerations and vendor assessment

As the landscape of Generative AI continues to evolve, this checklist may also be subject to change. Nevertheless, please consider the following questions when selecting an academic AI search tool.

1. Your research need, and the functionality/capabilities of a given AI search engine or research assistant.

Criteria	Further guidance and considerations	Assessment
1.1 What features are most relevant to your work?	<i>Consider all functionalities that the AI tool provides, such as advanced search capabilities, data visualization, and analysis of research trends, and more.</i>	
1.1.1 How does the tool integrate with the existing technologies you use for conducting literature reviews, such as reference management software or note-taking applications, etc.?	<i>The technologies you use might also evolve as more AI tools for research becomes available.</i>	
1.2 What are the sources of data that the LLM uses for generating results or on which it has been trained?		
1.3 If there are both free and fee-based versions available, what functionalities are included in the free version compared to those accessible in the fee-based version?	<i>Consider number of searches per week, visible references, number of records you can export, etc.</i>	
1.4 Does the tool customize recommendations based on your activities within the platform?	<i>Consider searches, document downloads, etc.</i>	

2. Your data privacy and security

Criteria	Further guidance and considerations	Assessment
2.1 Is your data (such as research activities, research inputs, or personal identifiers) being collected?	<i>Consider how your data is collected, stored, and processed.</i>	
2.1.1 Is your data being stored or shared with third parties?		YES / NO
2.1.2 Does the tool provide information regarding your rights related to data usage?	<i>Consider the option to opt-in or opt-out of data sharing for product enhancement or retention for training purposes.</i>	YES / NO
2.1.3 Does the tool adhere to confidentiality and security protocols to safeguard both institutional and individual research data?		YES / NO
2.1.4 Does the tool specify the ownership of user-generated content, including research outputs and personal data, with explicit descriptions of how this content can be used by the provider?		YES / NO
2.2 Does the tool require you to log in to individual accounts?		YES / NO

3. Your intellectual property

Criteria	Further guidance and considerations	Assessment
3.1 Does the search engine or research assistant include features that allow a user to upload or input their own intellectual property?	<i>Consider whether the content of a query includes your intellectual property. This might include your research data, a draft of a research paper, a grant application, etc.</i>	YES / NO
3.1.1 Does the tool offer liability protection for the misuse of your intellectual property?		YES / NO

3.1.2 Does the tool align with the anticipated University-wide policy regarding AI use?		YES / NO
3.1.3 Does the tool provide safeguards and restrictions related to usage data, personally identifiable information, and researcher intellectual property?		YES / NO
3.1.4 Does the tool outline intellectual property rights, ensuring protection for IP related to your research outputs (copyright, patent, etc.)?		YES / NO
3.2 Who will own the copyright of any outputs generated via queries that have used your intellectual property?	<i>Canadian copyright law has not settled the question of who owns the copyright of materials generated via an AI assistant.</i>	

4. Vendor ethics and business practices

Criteria	Further guidance and considerations	Assessment
4.1 Does the product documentation incorporate ethical considerations?	<i>Consider the mitigation of bias in algorithms, as well as ensuring transparency and reproducibility in the generation or ranking of results.</i>	YES / NO
4.2 Does the vendor commit to making changes if the community identifies specific ethical concerns or challenges?		YES / NO
4.3 How does the tool handle questions for where there is conflicting scientific evidence?		
4.4 Does the vendor engage in the development of best practices regarding the environmental impact of the Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) that power its tool?		YES / NO
4.5 Does the vendor prioritize scholarly integrity by upholding ethical standards in research,	Consider, for example, how is retracted research handled by the AI tool.	YES / NO

citation, and publication practices?		
4.6 Is the tool regularly updated and is the vendor committed to ongoing innovation and improvements?		YES / NO